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Educational Philosophies, Theories and Their Pedagogic Applicability in Schools and Colleges in Sierra Leone

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Abstract

This study looked into educational philosophies, theories and their pedagogic applicability in schools and colleges in Sierra Leone. Education is a consciously directed process that endows young people's souls with cultural values. It is a process by which the personality of the young is molded by restraining their primordial biological nature and causing them to accept and obey the human values developed in the course of history. The main part of this study focused on the philosophies and theories employed by teachers and lecturers in Sierra Leone and their applicability in the classroom and lecture room. Three hundred participants were drawn from schools and colleges with qualifications ranging from Teachers Certificate to Doctor of Philosophy. The study contends that the philosophy and theories employed by educators can most times lead to learning outcomes not being realized. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences was used to analyze the data and results interpreted quantitatively and qualitatively. From the data analyzed, teachers and lecturers confidently reported using the progressivist philosophy with 19% and pragmatism with 18% in the teaching and learning process. It was recommended though that there isn't a single clear cut philosophy that is employed by teachers and lecturers as the situation demands, the one of relative suitability in the Sierra Leonean pedagogic context is the progressivist philosophy which stands tall

Keywords: Educational philosophy, theory, traditionalism, pedagogical, applicability

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Education is a crucial factor in the social, political and economic development of any nation, in this regard, effective teaching is very essential. Effective teaching is important because teaching is based on helping children progress from one level to another in a more sociable interactive environment and to get the approach right to get students to be independent learners. Effectiveness in teaching does not necessarily mean being

perfect, mastering subject matter or giving a wonderful performance in teaching, but rather bringing out the best in your pupils and students.

Learning is defined as a process that brings together personal and environmental experiences and influences for acquiring, enriching or modifying one's knowledge, skills, values, attitudes, and behavior and world views. Learning theories therefore develop hypotheses that describe how this process takes place. Every teacher has his or her own method of teaching. As traditional teaching styles evolve with the advent of differentiated instruction, more and more teachers and lecturers are adjusting their approach depending on their students' learning needs. However, there are a few fundamental teaching methods most educators tend to use.

The term "teaching" in the classroom context is necessary and should be planned, it should have goals, but still it can be conducted on the basis of a particular philosophy or theory of learning. Teaching should not only be individualistic, but collaborative as well. Openness and making curricula, public will ensure social control (Op. Cit.: 50-59).Kansanem. Teaching is closely related to knowledge, learning and theories of learning. Constructivist theory is currently popular as a basis for understanding learning. (Puolimatka, 2002).

Philosophy means "love of wisdom." It is made up of two Greek words, "philo", meaning love, and "sophos", meaning wisdom. Philosophy helps teachers to reflect on key issues and concepts in education, usually through such questions as: What is being educated? What is the good life? What is knowledge? What is the nature of learning? And what is teaching? I think that philosophy in the classical sense is the love of wisdom. So the question then is 'What is wisdom?' And I think wisdom understands what really matters in the world." **Thomas Pogge**

A teacher or lecturer's educational philosophy is his or her beliefs about why, what and how he or she teaches, whom he teaches, and about the nature of learning. In dispensing this philosophy, pedagogic principles are taken note of; these are principles that guide professional action through the events and issues teachers face in their daily discharge of their duties. Sources for a teacher and lecturer's educational philosophy are their life experiences, values, the environment they live in, interactions with others.

On examining a philosophy that is different from one's own, it helps to do introspection with one's own thinking. Sometimes this means you may change your mind. Other times, it may strengthen your perspective; or, you may be eclectic, selecting what seems best from different philosophies. But in eclecticism, there is a danger of sloppy and inconsistent thinking, especially if you borrow a bit of one philosophy and stir in some other. If serious thought is given to selection of strategies, theories, or philosophies in a teachers or lecturer's pedagogic assignment, there would be less problem in the actualization of learning outcomes in the teaching and learning process. In this way, the teacher or lecturer may determine how to vary his or her approach depending on the particular learning needs and styles of the pupils and students. At various points in the teaching and learning situation, one philosophical framework may become favored over another. For example, the Progressive movement led to quite different approaches in education in the 1930s. But there is always danger in one "best or only" philosophy. In a pluralistic society a variety of views are needed.

Learners are different by nature; they have their different likes and dislikes. There is a wise saying that "If you want to teach X Mathematics, you should not only know mathematics, but should know X as well". This entails having a broader knowledge about the learner regarding his or her physical, mental, social and emotional orientations. Successful application of philosophies and theories in the classroom, thus hinges on learner readiness.

Knowledge of one's learning styles can be used to increase self-awareness about their strengths and weaknesses as learners. In other words, all the advantages claimed for metacognition (being aware of one's own thought and

learning process) can be gained by encouraging learners to become knowledgeable about their own learning and that of others. (Coffield, et.al. 2004).

The frame of reference for general didactics is formed by the “interaction outlining models”, the “method, consciousness describing models” and the “models for studying persons involved in a teaching situation” (Kansanen, 1992). Kansanen (1991) studied about teachers’ pedagogical thinking and said that “pedagogical thinking is a basic skill behind the teaching of teachers and it is also a basic problem of teacher education”. Hence pedagogical thinking is also applicable in pupil and student education.

The poor performance of pupils in the 2008 Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) and West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) in Sierra Leone prompted His Excellency the President to set up a Commission of Inquiry comprising: Professor Sahr P. Thomas Gbamanja as Chairman, Professor Ekundayo J.D. Thompson, Dr. Bamidele O. Sannoh, Mr. Nabie M. Kamara (Late), Mr. Akiwade J. Lasite as Members and Saa Kpulun (Permanent Secretary) as Secretary, with the key terms of reference including:

To investigate and identify the reasons for the poor performance of pupils in the BECE and WASSC Examinations in Sierra Leone, taking into account the role played by the teachers and their attitudes and methodologies amongst others. Thus, this study is designed to look into the philosophies of teachers and their theories used in the discharge of their duties.

Teachers and lecturers alike are expected to have a teaching philosophy statement that encapsulates their conception of teaching and learning, a description of how they teach and a rationale why they teach that way.

1.1 EDUCATION IN SIERRA LEONE

Education in Sierra Leone (1960s – 1970s) In 1958, three years before the country gained the status of being an independent nation-state, the first major White Paper on Education in Sierra Leone was published, declaring, “the ultimate goal must, of course, be the establishment of fee-free universal compulsory education” (Sierra Leone Government White Paper, 1958, p. 1). At that early stage, the long-term aim was not “merely to produce literates but to enable pupils to make a beginning in obtaining the necessary mental equipment to enjoy a fuller, happier life and thereby make a greater contribution to the welfare and development of the community as a whole” (Sierra Leone Government White Paper, 1958, p. 1- 2). By the 1970s, as Western academics grew critical of whether universal education was in reality a sensible aim, the elevated optimism of the previous decade became increasingly muted.

To address these disparities, as well as the slow increase in enrollment rates, President Siaka Probyn Stevens then called for a Sierra Leone Education Review – a comprehensive survey of the education system that brought together staff of the University of Sierra Leone, government administrators, and international consultants for series of meetings in 1973.

The Bunumbu Project (1974 – late 1980s). In 1974, the Government of Sierra Leone called upon the United Nations Special Fund and UNESCO to assist in implementing the Bunumbu Project – a program designed to make schools more relevant and central to rural communities. Specifically, the project translated the National Development Plan of accelerating primary school expansion into the following strategic objectives:

- i) Development of a new primary curriculum with a rural bias;
- ii) Expansion of existing functions of the teacher training colleges and
- iii) Development of a countrywide network of community educational centers providing both formal and non-formal education and training for young people and adults in the rural areas.

Like other former British Colonies, Sierra Leone followed a modified form of the British System of Education, consisting of a primary school of 7 years duration and a secondary school of 5 years, followed by few cases of 2 years of sixth form study and 4 years of university education.

This trend, however, changed in the 1993 school year with the introduction of the 6-3-3-4 system of schooling, that is, 6 years of Primary, 3 years of Junior Secondary, 3 years of Senior Secondary and 4 years of University/Polytechnic for those who can get to that level.

You may have missed it, but the Sierra Leone education system has been modified from 6-3-3-4 to the new 6-3-4-4 system (Gbamanja report). With the former, learners spent 6 years in primary school, 3 years in junior secondary, 3 years in senior secondary and 4 years in university. With the latter, students will spend another one year in Senior Secondary School (SSS).

As the back and forth system of education continues in Sierra Leone, the new government that came to power in April 2018 has again reverted the educational system to the former 6-3-3-4 system.

1.2 RESEARCH AIM

The general aim of this research is to ascertain the applicability of the pedagogic philosophies and or theories employed by teachers and lecturers in the teaching and learning situation in schools and colleges in Sierra Leone.

The objectives of the study are:

- a) Identifying the philosophy most used by teachers and lecturers
- b) Assess the suitability of pedagogic theories used by these educators
- c) Ascertain the relevance of the theories and philosophies employed in our present educational system.
- d) Proffer possible alternatives to some of the theories and philosophies used.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Many professors report feeling inadequately prepared by their graduate school experiences to fulfill their teaching responsibilities effectively (Beckerman, 2010). While many professors have an extensive knowledge base in their respective academic fields, they have very little knowledge about how to teach their content in effective ways (Beckerman, 2010). Unfortunately, this lack of adequate pedagogical preparation often leads to the implementation of poor-quality courses for students.

Because one's teaching philosophy directly impacts one's practice within the classroom (Gossman, 2008) it is imperative that teachers and lecturers closely examine the principles that guide their teaching.

Students tend to engage more and work harder in classroom contexts where they (students) believe the instructor sincerely cares about what he or she has to say (Barnett, 2011).

2.1 PHILOSOPHY OF EDUCATION

This can refer either to the application of philosophy to the problem of education, examining definitions, goals and chains of meaning used in education by teachers, administrators and policymakers. It can involve the examination of particular visions or approaches by researchers and policy-makers in education that often address contemporary debates and assumptions about innovations and practices in teaching and learning by considering the profession within broader philosophical or sociocultural contexts.

The philosophy of education may be either the philosophy of the process of education or the philosophy of the education discipline. "That is, it may be part of the discipline in the sense of being concerned with the aims, forms, methods, or results of the process of educating or being educated; or it may be metadisciplinary in the sense of being concerned with the concepts, aims, and methods of the discipline."

As such, it is both part of the field of education and a field of applied philosophy, drawing from fields of metaphysics, epistemology, axiology and the philosophical approaches (speculative, prescriptive, or analytic) to address questions in and about pedagogy, education policy, and curriculum, as well as the process of learning, to name a few. For example, it might study what constitutes upbringing and education, the values and norms revealed through upbringing and educational practices, the limits and legitimization of education as an academic discipline, and the relation between educational theory and practice. One application is transactionalism which seeks to avoid the risks of simplifying complexity in teaching and learning any subject.

2.1.1 IDEALISM

Idealism is a philosophical approach that has as its central tenet that ideas are the only true reality, the only thing worth knowing. In a search for truth, beauty, and justice that is enduring and everlasting; the focus is on conscious reasoning in the mind. Plato, the father of Idealism, espoused this view about 400 years BC, in his famous book, *The Republic*. Plato believed that there are two worlds. The first is the spiritual or mental world, which is eternal, permanent, orderly, regular, and universal. There is also the world of appearance, the world experienced through sight, touch, smell, taste, and sound that is changing imperfect, and disorderly. This division is often referred to as the duality of mind and body. Reacting against what he perceived as too much of a focus on the immediacy of the physical and sensory world, Plato described a utopian society in which "education to body and soul all the beauty and perfection of which they are capable" as an ideal.

In idealism, the aim of education is to discover and develop each individual's abilities and full moral excellence in order to better serve society. The curricular emphasis is the subject matter of mind: literature, history, philosophy, and religion. Teaching methods focus on handling ideas through lecture, discussion, and Socratic dialogue (a method of teaching that uses questioning to help students discover and clarify knowledge). Introspection, intuition, insight, and whole-part logic are used to bring to consciousness the forms or concepts which are latent in the mind. Character is developed through emulating examples of heroes and heroines.

2.1.2 REALISM

Realists believe that reality exists independent of the human mind. The ultimate reality is the world of physical objects. The focus is on the body/objects. Truth is objective-what can be observed. Aristotle, a student of Plato who broke with his mentor's idealist philosophy, is called the father of both Realism and the scientific method. In this metaphysical view, the aim is to understand objective reality through "the diligent and unsparing scrutiny of all observable data." Aristotle believed that to understand an object, its ultimate form had to be understood, which does not change. For example, a rose exists whether or not a person is aware of it. A rose can exist in the mind without being physically present, but ultimately, the rose shares properties with all other roses and flowers (its form), although one rose may be red and another peach colored. Aristotle also was the first to teach logic as a formal discipline in order to be able to reason about physical events and aspects. The exercise of rational thought is viewed as the ultimate purpose for humankind. The Realist curriculum emphasizes the subject matter of the physical world, particularly science and mathematics. The teacher organizes and presents content systematically within a discipline, demonstrating use of criteria in making decisions. Teaching methods focus on mastery of facts and basic skills through demonstration and recitation. Students must also demonstrate the ability to think critically and scientifically, using observation and

2.1.3 PRAGMATISM (EXPERIENTIALISM)

Pragmatists believe that only those things that are experienced or observed are real. In this late 19th century American philosophy, the focus is on the reality of experience. Unlike the Realists and Rationalists, Pragmatists believe that reality is constantly changing and that we learn best through applying our experiences and thoughts to problems, as they arise. The universe is dynamic and evolving, a "becoming" view of the world. There is no absolute and unchanging truth, but rather, truth is what works. Pragmatism is derived from the teaching of

Charles Sanders Peirce (1839-1914), who believed that thought must produce action, rather than linger in the mind and lead to indecisiveness.

Pragmatists teaching methods focus on hands-on problem solving, experimenting, and projects, often having students work in groups. The pragmatist curriculum should bring the disciplines together to focus on solving problems in an interdisciplinary way. Rather than passing down organized bodies of knowledge to new learners, Pragmatists believe that learners should apply their knowledge to real situations through experimental inquiry. This prepares students for citizenship, daily living, and future careers.

2.1.4. PROGRESSIVISM

Educational progressivism is the belief that education must be based on the principle that humans are social animals who learn best in real-life activities with other people. Progressivist-like proponents of most educational theories, claim to rely on the best available scientific theories of learning. Most progressive educators believe that children learn as if they were scientists, following a process similar to John Dewey's model of learning known as "the pattern of inquiry": 1) Become aware of the problem. 2) Define the problem. 3) Propose hypotheses to solve it. 4) Evaluate the consequences of the hypotheses from one's past experience and 5) Test the likeliest solution.

2.1.5 TRADITIONALIST

Traditionalists are mental disciplinarians, espousing the belief that if you exercise the mind like any muscle it will get stronger. They encourage rigorous mental involvement to strengthen the mind; traditionalist theory is based on perennialist and essentialist philosophies which are outgrowths of realism and idealism. Perennialism is one of the earliest educational philosophies, where reality is a world of reason and God, truth is in reason and revelation, and goodness is in rationality. Schools exist to reveal God's will, and the instructional objective is to educate the rational person and to cultivate the intellect. Schools exist to sharpen the minds and intellectual processes. The instructional objective is to promote the intellectual growth of the individual. The major difference between essentialism and Perennialism is that essentialism calls for core courses.

2.1.6 EXISTENTIALISM

The nature of reality for Existentialists is subjective, and lies within the individual. The physical world has no inherent meaning outside of human existence. Individual choice and individual standards rather than external standards are central. Existence comes before any definition of what we are. We define ourselves in relationship to that existence by the choices we make. We should not accept anyone else's predetermined philosophical system; rather, we must take responsibility for deciding who we are. The focus is on freedom, the development of authentic individuals, as we make meaning of our lives.

There are several different orientations within the existentialist philosophy. Soren Kierkegaard (1813-1855), a Danish minister and philosopher, is considered to be the founder of existentialism. He was of a Christian orientation. Another group of existentialists, largely European, believes that we must recognize the finiteness of our lives on this small and fragile planet, rather than believing in salvation through God. Our existence is not guaranteed in an afterlife, so there is tension about life and the certainty of death, of hope or despair. Unlike the more austere European approaches where the universe is seen as meaningless when faced with the certainty of the end of existence.

2.2 EDUCATIONAL THEORIES OF LEARNING

Related to both the metaphysical world view philosophies and the educational philosophies are theories of learning that focus on how learning occurs; the psychological orientations. They provide structure for the instructional aspects of teaching, suggesting methods that relate to their perspective on learning. These

theoretical beliefs about learning are also at the cognitive level of philosophy, as they are concerned with the nature of learning. Each psychological orientation is directly related to a particular educational philosophy, but may have other influences as well. The first two theoretical approaches discussed below can be thought of as transmissive, in that information is given to learners. The second two approaches are constructivist, in that the learner has to make meaning from experiences in the world.

2.2.1 INFORMATION PROCESSING

Information Processing theorists focus on the mind and how it works to explain how learning occurs. The focus is on the processing of a relatively fixed body of knowledge and how it is attended to, received in the mind, processed, stored, and retrieved from memory. This model is derived from analogies between how the brain works and computer processing. Information processing theorists focus on the individual rather than the social aspects of thinking and learning. (Atkinson & Shrifin)

Knowledge may be general, applicable to many situations; for example, knowing how to type or spell. Other knowledge is domain specific, applicable to a specific subject or task, such as vowel sounds in languages. Knowledge is also *declarative* (content, or knowing *that*; for example, schools have students, teachers, and administrators), *procedural* (knowing *how* to do things—the steps or strategies; for example, to multiply mixed number, change both sides to improper fractions, then multiply numerators and denominators), or *conditional* (knowing *when* and *why* to apply the other two types of knowledge; for example, when taking a standardized multiple choice test, keep track of time, be strategic, and don't get bogged down on hard problems).

2.2.2 BEHAVIORISM

Behaviorist theorists believe that behavior is shaped deliberately by forces in the environment and that the type of person and actions desired can be the product of design. In other words, behavior is determined by others, rather than by our own free will. By carefully shaping desirable behavior, morality and information is learned. Learners will acquire and remember responses that lead to satisfying aftereffects. Repetition of a meaningful connection results in learning. If the student is ready for the connection, learning is enhanced; if not, learning is inhibited. Motivation to learn is the satisfying after effect, or reinforcement. (Thorndike E.L, Pavlov, I Skinner, B.F, Bandura, A).All behavior can be explained without the need to consider internal mental states or consciousness (Watson, B).

Both positive reinforcement and negative reinforcement increase the probability that the antecedent behavior will happen again. In contrast, punishment (both positive and negative) decreases the likelihood that the antecedent behavior will happen again. Positive indicates the application of a stimulus; Negative indicates the withholding of a stimulus. Lots of (early) behaviorist work was done with animals (e.g. Pavlov's dogs) and generalized to humans (Skinner B.F)

Ivan Pavlov's research on using the reinforcement of a bell sound when food was presented to a dog and finding the sound alone would make a dog salivate after several presentations of the conditioned stimulus, was the beginning of behaviorist approaches. Learning occurs as a result of responses to stimuli in the environment that are reinforced by adults and others, as well as from feedback from actions on objects. The teacher can help students learn by conditioning them through identifying the desired behaviors in measurable, observable terms, recording these behaviors and their frequencies, identifying appropriate reinforcers for each desired behavior, and providing the reinforcer as soon as the student displays the behavior.

2.2.3 HUMANISM

Humanism is a paradigm/philosophy/pedagogical approach that believes learning is viewed as a personal act to fulfill one's potential. The roots of humanism are found in the thinking of Erasmus (1466-1536), who attacked the religious teaching and thought prevalent in his time to focus on free inquiry and the rediscovery of the classical roots from Greece and Rome. Erasmus believed in the essential goodness of children, that humans have free will, moral conscience, and the ability to reason, aesthetic sensibility, and religious instinct. He advocated that the young should be treated kindly and that learning should not be forced or rushed, as it proceeds in stages.

Humanism was developed as an educational philosophy by Rousseau (1712-1778) and Pestalozzi. They emphasized nature and the basic goodness of human's understanding through the senses, and education as a gradual and an unhurried process in which the development of human character follows the unfolding of nature. Humanists believe that the learner should be in control of his or her own destiny. Since the learner should become a fully autonomous person, personal freedom, choice, and responsibility are the focus. The learner is self-motivated to achieve towards the highest level possible. Motivation to learn is intrinsic in humanism.

Recent applications of humanist philosophy focus on the social and emotional well-being of the child, as well as the cognitive. Development of a healthy self-concept, awareness of the psychological needs, helping students to strive to be all that they can are important concepts, espoused in theories of Abraham Maslow, Carl Rogers, and Alfred Adler that are found in classrooms today. Teachers emphasize freedom from threat, emotional well-being, and learning.

2.2.4 COGNITIVISM

The cognitivist paradigm essentially argues that the "black box" of the mind should be opened and understood. The learner is viewed as an information processor (like a computer).

Cognitive psychology was initiated in the late 1950s, and contributed to the move away from behaviourism. People are no longer viewed as collections of responses to external stimuli, as understood by behaviourists, but information processors. Cognitive psychology paid attention to complex mental phenomena, ignored by behaviourists, and was influenced by the emergence of the computer as an information-processing device, which became analogous to the human mind. In cognitive psychology, learning is understood as the acquisition of knowledge: the learner is an information-processor who absorbs information, undertakes cognitive operations on it, and sticks it in memory. Therefore, its preferred methods of instruction are lecturing and reading textbooks; and, at its most extreme, the learner is a passive recipient of knowledge by the teacher.

The cognitivist revolution replaced behaviorism in the 1960s as the dominant paradigm. Cognitivism focuses on the inner mental activities that is; opening the "black box" of the human mind is valuable and necessary for understanding how people learn. Mental processes such as thinking, memory, knowing, and problem-solving need to be explored. Knowledge can be seen as schema or symbolic mental constructions. Learning is defined as a change in a learner's schema. (Marriner David Merrill 1937, Charles Reigeluth 1946)

2.2.5 CONSTRUCTIVISM

Constructivism emerged in the 1970s and 1980s, giving rise to the idea that learners are not passive recipients of information, but that they actively construct their knowledge in interaction with the environment and through the reorganization of their mental structures. Learners are therefore viewed as sense-makers, not simply recording given information but interpreting it. This view of learning led to the shift from the "knowledge-acquisition" to "knowledge-construction" metaphor. The growing evidence in support of the constructive nature of learning was also in line with and backed by the earlier work of influential theorists such as Jean Piaget and Jerome Bruner. While there are different versions of constructivism, what is found in common is the learner-

centered approach whereby the teacher becomes a cognitive guide of learner’s learning and not a knowledge transmitter.

A reaction to didactic approaches such as behaviorism and programmed instruction, constructivism states that learning is an active, contextualized process of constructing knowledge rather than acquiring it. Knowledge is constructed based on personal experiences and hypotheses of the environment. Learners continuously test these hypotheses through social negotiation. Each person has a different interpretation and construction of knowledge process. (Dewey & Bruner J). The learner is not a blank slate (Tabula rasa) but brings past experiences and cultural factors to a situation.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted using the survey method. Interviews were conducted, questionnaires designed and administered to respondents in the selected educational institutions in Sierra Leone. Before conducting the research, the consent of the participants was sought and they kindly consented to participate and complete the questionnaire. They were briefed on the questionnaire, the objectives and purpose of the research. The survey is associated with the teaching and lecture methods of teachers and lecturers in schools and colleges in Sierra Leone. Observation of educators was also carried out. The study allows for the collection of quantitative data which would be analyzed quantitatively using descriptive and inferential statistics. Secondary data were derived from books, journals, and websites. Through random sampling, 300 respondents consisting of teachers and lecturers formed the sample from nursery, primary, secondary schools and tertiary institutions. A quantitative approach was considered appropriate for use to ascertain the cause-effect relationship between the variables. The data were analyzed in tables, and the corresponding values expressed in percentages.

4.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1: PHILOSOPHIES USED BY TEACHERS/LECTURERS OF VARIOUS EDUCATIONAL LEVELS IN SIERRA LEONE

VARIABLES	EDUCATIONAL LEVEL					Total
	TEACHERS CERTIFICATE	HIGHER TEACHERS CERTIFICATE	BACHELOR DEGREE	MASTER DEGREE	DOCTORAL DEGREE	
EXISTENTIALISM	12 20.0%	9 15.0%	11 18.3%	9 12.0%	7 15.6%	48 16.0%
IDEALISM	9 15.0%	4 6.7%	9 15.0%	11 14.7%	8 17.8%	41 13.7%
REALISM	7 11.7%	10 16.7%	14 23.3%	13 17.3%	8 17.8%	52 17.3%
PRAGMATISM	11 18.3%	18 30.0%	8 13.3%	10 13.3%	9 20.0%	56 18.7%
PROGRESSIVISM	15 25.0%	13 21.7%	9 15.0%	15 20.0%	6 13.3%	58 19.3%
TRADITIONALISM	6 10.0%	6 10.0%	9 15.0%	17 22.7%	7 15.6%	45 15.0%
Total	60 100.0%	60 100.0%	60 100.0%	75 100.0%	45 100.0%	300 100.0%

Table 1 describes the philosophy used by different categories of teachers and lecturers in the teaching profession in Sierra Leone. According to the above table, 20% of Teachers Certificate (TC) holders, use the existentialism philosophy, while 15% of them use the idealist philosophy. Those who use the Realist philosophy were 18% of the TC holders and 18% use the pragmatist ideology. A majority of them measures, 25% used the progressivist ideology to teach and 10% of them used that of the traditionalist.

For the Higher Teachers certificate (HTC) holders, 30% of them used the pragmatist ideology, while 22% used the progressivist ideology and 16% used the realist philosophy. Those in the Bachelor degree category put more emphasis on the realist philosophy as 23% of them used that philosophy. Unlike those with Master Degree who preferred using the philosophy of traditionalism as 23% of them affirmed that they used it. Also, 20% of them used the philosophy of progressivism and 17% used the realist philosophy. 20% of respondents from the doctoral category used the pragmatist ideology during lectures, while 18% used both the idealist and realist philosophy. The table shows that the three most employed philosophies across the respondents are progressivism 58%, pragmatism 56% and realism 52%. Considering the diverse subject areas taught by these educators, the analysis shows that the sciences, Arts, Social sciences and Humanities are appropriate areas for the employment of these philosophies. The pragmatic approach used by teachers and lecturers in Sierra Leone is gaining some impact on the teaching of practical oriented subjects in schools and colleges.

Table 2: THEORIES USED MOST BY TEACHERS/LECTURERS AT VARIOUS EDUCATIONAL LEVELS IN SIERRA LEONE

VARIABLES	EDUCATIONAL LEVEL					Total
	TEACHERS CERTIFICATE	HIGHER TEACHERS CERTIFICATE	BACHELOR DEGREE	MASTER DEGREE	DOCTORAL DEGREE	
INFORMATION PROCESS	10 16.7%	15 25.0%	11 18.3%	10 13.3%	11 24.4%	57 19.0%
BEHAVIORISM	15 25.0%	7 11.7%	11 18.3%	18 24.0%	12 26.7%	63 21.0%
COGNITIVISM	13 21.7%	17 28.3%	11 18.3%	17 22.7%	7 15.6%	65 21.7%
CONSTRUCTIVISM	6 10.0%	12 20.0%	17 28.3%	13 17.3%	5 11.1%	53 17.7%
HUMANISM	16 26.7%	9 15.0%	10 16.7%	17 22.7%	10 22.2%	62 20.7%
Total	60 100.0%	60 100.0%	60 100.0%	75 100.0%	45 100.0%	300 100.0%

Table 2 describes the theory that is used most by the various categories of certificate holders. Those with TC used more of the humanism theory as 27% of the respondents used it. 25% of the same category used the information process theory and 22% used the cognitivist theory. Within the HTC holders, 28% of them preferred using the cognitivist theory, whereas 25% were comfortable using the information process theory. 20% were convenient with the use of the constructivist theory. Most teachers with bachelor degree believe in the constructivist theory as 28% of its membership admitted using this theory. Unlike the information process theory, the behaviorist theory and the cognitivist theory with 18% each of applicability by these teachers. 24% of Master holders used more of behaviorist theory than all the others, 23% used both the cognitivist and traditional theories, 17% preferred the constructivist theory. 27% of doctorate holders confirmed using the behaviourist theory, 24% used the information process theory, and 22% affirmed they used the humanist theory. Behaviorism, cognitivism and humanism stands out as most used theories by the respondents as 21%, 21% and 20% respectively is the reported total responses.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 CONCLUSION

Teachers and lecturers who believed in the behaviorist theory hold the view that there is no such thing as free will learning, but that learning is a physiological response to stimuli. They believe that human nature is innately neither good nor bad, but is shaped by the environment which can help modify behavior and manage contingencies of learners. They used positive rather than negative, reinforcement to shape and refine learning, programmed learning, and healthy classroom climate. Extensive use of audio-visual aids by lecturers and teaching aids by teachers was realized at some point in the teaching and learning process.

From the research, the progressivist teachers and lecturers relate their style of pedagogy to the application of experience and science to solve problems. They believe that the school and college are a microcosm of society that have real-life curriculum with an emphasis on problem-solving. It attends to and optimizes inquisitive, active learning style of pupils and students as they learn from each other, cooperative groups thereby making the teaching and learning child centered.

The Existentialist believes in the education of the whole person and subject matter takes second place to develop a positive self - concept, self-knowledge, and self-responsibility. Students are allowed to choose their subject matters. The learning process is based objectively on changes in behavior. This is a philosophy that emphasizes the uniqueness and isolation of the individual experience in a hostile or in different universe, regards human existence as unexplainable and stresses freedom of choice and responsibility for the consequences of one's acts.

It was observed from the behaviorist educators that learning begins when a cue or stimulus from the environment is presented and the learner reacts to the stimulus with some type of response. A teacher was observed presenting an object for pupils to describe. Consequences that reinforce the desired behavior are arranged to follow the desired behavior (e.g. Round of applause for best description). The new behavioral pattern can be repeated hence becomes automatic. The relative change in the behavior of the learner signifies that learning has occurred. Teachers use behaviorism when they reward or punish student behaviors.

Constructivist theorists believe that learning is a process where individuals construct new ideas or concepts based on prior knowledge and/or experience. Constructivism assumes that all knowledge is constructed from the learner's previous knowledge, regardless of how one is taught. Thus, even listening to a lecture involves active attempts to construct new knowledge.(Vygotsky M,L, Dewey J et al)

Unlike behaviorism, cognitive information processing is governed by an internal process rather than by external circumstance. Teachers asked thought provoking questions for learners to think and respond. Behavior changes were realized in learners as they showed some somatic cues in answering to cognitive questions. Such cues were indicators as to what was happening in the learner's mind. The teachers' cognitive theory employed paid more attention to what goes on inside the learner's head and focuses on mental processes rather than observable behavior.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Teachers and lecturers upon starting their pedagogic responsibilities are faced with a series of questions like would the students be comfortable with the methodology? Would my goals be achieved? Would there be a positive classroom climate? Which assessment strategy would be used? A question that definitely needs immediate answer before teaching is what methods would I use to teach? Against this background, it is prudent that teachers and lecturers develop a philosophy that best exemplifies the way they want to facilitate the learning process of their pupils and students. Thus a variety of aspects from past philosophers of education in conjunction with the teachers' situational demands have to be employed.

Lecturers and teachers should change their form of interaction and how they relate to students in and out of the lecture or classroom. They should see pupils or students as co-teachers in the classroom and the teaching and learning process as one wherein both teachers and students together develop ideas and learn from each other.

The general educational philosophy called progressivism, sometimes also called constructivism is highly recommended, as educators, we closely relate to this philosophy because it is identified as a philosophy where learners are active and self-motivated, and learners are recognized as having unique needs and interests that can be used in the teaching and learning process. Teachers or lecturers should serve as facilitators, using the interests and needs of the pupils or students to nurture their desire to learn as they create an active and interesting classroom climate thereby allowing for the learners' natural interest and activeness to take root. This

theory presupposes that learners take full responsibility of learning outcomes and not the “fill the jar” style of instruction where the learner is spoon fed.

Assessing learners is crucial in the teaching and learning process and teachers and lecturers should endeavor to carry it out be it formative or summative. Some formative assessment practices in the form of observations, checklists, written response assignments, demonstrations, discussions and self-reflections are prudent.

The training of all untrained and unqualified teachers throughout the country should continue through well-structured training programs, followed by improved conditions of service for teachers and lecturers.

Lecturers should move beyond seeing teaching as a process of merely transferring knowledge and skills and focus towards a broader view of teaching as a process of precipitating social and intellectual change in and among students.

The modern method of teaching which is a more interacting and student-based teaching should take premium over the traditional method of teaching where a teacher directs students to learn through memorization and recitation techniques thereby not developing their critical thinking problem solving and decision making skills.

Lecturers should begin their courses by establishing a positive working relationship with their students and assess their students’ needs, interests, and abilities. This can be done by administering a pre-course survey on the initial day of class to clearly identify students’ personal concerns, learning preferences, and background experiences related to the course requirements and objectives.

The code of ethics designed for teachers and lecturers should be enforced while adequate provision of teaching and learning materials are made.

Given the giant leap in Information Technology (IT), teachers, lecturers and students should not be left out in this race. Thus, it is hereby recommended that the “21st Century Skills” initiative, which is an education standards and reform movement focusing on improving what pupils and students must learn in school to better prepare them succeed in their school and career lives should be pursued. These “21st century skills” include the following skill sets:

Life/career skills: adaptability & flexibility, initiative & self-direction, leadership & responsibility, productivity & accountability, social & cross-cultural skills.

Core subjects: English/language arts, mathematics, arts, science, history, geography and others.

21st century themes: civic literacy, environmental literacy, financial literacy (including economic, business, and entrepreneurial skills), global awareness, health literacy.

Information/media/technology skills: media literacy, information literacy.

Learning/innovation skills: creativity, critical thinking, collaboration, communication, problem solving. (Jenkins, H.*et al* 2009)

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